

Effect of age of dhaincha on green and dry matter production and nitrogen added, Ludhiana, India.

Age of dhaincha (days)	Green matter (t/ha)	Dry matter (t/ha)	N added (kg/ha)
30	1.6	0.23	8.3
45	15.6	2.03	57.9
60	28.9	5.58	132.0

without dhaincha received basal P applied to rice. The dhaincha crops were buried one day before transplanting on 4 July.

Amount of green matter, dry matter, and N added increased with increasing dhaincha age (see table). In effect on yield, 60-day-old dhaincha alone was equal to 120 kg N/ha applied as urea; 45-day-old dhaincha was equal to 60 kg N/ha; 30-day-old dhaincha did not increase yield substantially (see figure). □

Effect of age of dhaincha green manure on N economy in rice. Ludhiana, India.

Improvement of crop stand in flooded rice fields

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Direct-seeded rice fields inundated soon after seeding — not infrequent in rainfed lowlands — show suboptimal stands. In controlled greenhouse investigations on improving the germination and crop stand for such situations, seeds soaked in a 1% solution of oxidizing chemicals such as hydrogen peroxide, potassium permanganate, or potassium dichromate for 24 hours were sown in moist soil and immediately flooded with 10, 20, and 40 cm water.

Seeds soaked in hydrogen peroxide and potassium permanganate showed higher germination (90-95%) under different floodwater depths. Seeds soaked in potassium dichromate had drastically reduced germination (40-50%). Seeds soaked in hydrogen peroxide produced vigorous seedlings that emerged rapidly, even from 40-cm-deep floodwater.

The study indicates the possibility of improving crop stands in direct-sown flooded ricefields by soaking the seed in hydrogen peroxide and potassium permanganate. □

Effect of azolla manuring with nitrogen fertilization

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The effect on rice grain yield of incorporating azolla into soil fertilized with nitrogen was studied in a field trial during 1979 rabi. The azolla levels tested were 0, 10, 20, and 30 t/ha; the N fertilizer levels, 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha; and the rice variety, ADT 31. Azolla levels formed the main treatment and nitrogen levels, the subtreatment. The treatments were repli-

cated twice. Azolla was incorporated 1 week before planting; nitrogen as urea was applied in one basal dose. P₂O₅ and K₂O at 50 kg/ha were applied just before planting. The addition of azolla at all levels and of nitrogen at all levels gave significantly higher yields (see table). □

Effect of azolla manuring along with nitrogen applications on grain yield of ADT 31, 1979 rabi, Aduthurai, India

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Mean (N levels)
	with azolla incorporated at				
	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20 t/ha	30 t/ha	
0	3.4	3.8	4.2	4.6	4.0
25	3.8	4.4	4.7	5.0	4.5
50	4.2	4.7	5.3	5.6	4.9
75	4.5	5.3	5.8	6.1	5.4
100	5.0	6.0	6.4	6.8	6.0
Mean (azolla levels)	4.2	4.8	5.3	5.4	
C.D.	Azolla levels 0.3		N levels 0.2		Interaction N.S.

Performance of rice transplanted under nonpuddled rainfed conditions

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Ragi *Eleusine coracana G.*, an important millet crop of Karnataka, is transplanted on the sides of ridges, then irrigated. A study was conducted to determine whether like ragi, rice could be transplanted under nonpuddled conditions and whether the subsequent rice crop could be grown under rainfed conditions, and given protective irrigation where necessary. A successful crop under these conditions would mean considerable water savings.

The test field was tilled during the early rains of the season. Ridges 20 cm